

USE OF THE ISPRING PROGRAM IN THE ORGANIZATION OF IMMUNOLOGY CLASSES

S.A.Navruzova

Student Navoi State Pedagogical Institut

Abstract: This article highlights the benefits of using modern computer technologies, especially the ispring program, in the teaching of immunology.

Key words: Modern computer technologies, ispring program, ispring pro, ispring suite, ispring quizmarker.

The creation of electronic information educational resources (EATR) in the continuing education system is one of the current issues. Before describing the software analysis, let's show what goes into EAT resources.

EAT resources include subject-specific electronic textbooks, study guides, instructional manuals, multimedia tools, reference books and dictionaries, hypertexts, electronic tests and assignments, and the like to support independent student learning. includes engaging, educational resources.

In addition to the above resources, pedagogical software tools, video and audio lectures, virtual laboratory stands, and interactive posters can be included. One of the widely used software for creating EAT resources is Ispring

The program is usually used to conduct a presentation Microsoft Power Point software is used in most cases during the preparation process. But such presentations can only be in the format of this product (ppt, pptx). Currently, the development of Internet technologies and, in turn, distance as a result of the emergence of the educational type, presentation files must be in flash (swf) format or based on HTML 5 technology in order to directly view them online in the Internet browser itself. So far, it has been prepared in PowerPoint programs have been created that make it possible to create a flash video from the presentation. The product is called iSpring and has variants such as iSpring Free, iSpring PRO and iSpring Presenter. [<http://www.ispringsolutions.com>]. According to independent experts, the speed of this product, the quality of conversion from one format to another format and the number of options is one of the best. iSpring not only allows you to create flash presentations, but also allows you to create videos that can be used in the educational process, in particular, including various forms of surveys, electronic tests, and the possibility of interactive communication will give.

iSpring has the following options:

- possibility to convert presentation files in several (exe, swf, html) formats;
- the ability to include external resources (audio, video or flash files) in the content of the presentation;
- protection of the content of the presentation: viewing with the help of a password, a "protection symbol" for the presentation placing, "rotating" the presentation only in permitted domains;
- add video and synchronize it with animations;
- a tool for creating electronic tests (controls) and creating interactive texts with the ability to send the results to e-mail or to a distance learning system (LMS) built-in (Quiz button);
- SCORM/AICC-compliant courses for use in the distance learning system Create;
- ActionScript API for scrolling at the presentation program level;
- record a video and synchronize it with the presentation;
- The possibility to include YouTube videos in the content of the presentation.

Figure 1. ispring window

The interface of the iSpring program iSpring Kinetics to create references and glossaries within EAT resources program can be cited.

iSpring Visuals has the following key features:

- a convenient electronic glossary, reference or creating a dictionary;
- creating a time scale;
- Creating a 3-dimensional book;
- FAQ can be created.

A state-of-the-art computer-aided creator of online presentations and e-learning courses one of the programs is iSpring Suite. iSpring Suite includes iSpringPro, iSpring QuizMaker, iSpring Kinetics. Among these programs is the iSpring QuizMaker program creates interactive tests and questionnaires using audio, video files, images and formulas.

iSpring to PC to create interactive quizzes using iSpring QuizMaker software

Adobe Flash (32-bit and 64-bit depending on the version of the operating system) with the suite it is required to be installed. after installing the program, in the Vse programmy section from the Start menu iSpring Suite will be selected.

Figure 2. Quizmarker window

If we select Sozdat novyy test section from this window, a window for creating pedagogical tests will open. This window is the working window of the program. Test from the Dobavit test section of the working window the creation process begins. This section lists 11 types of pedagogical tests we can create a test by choosing what is needed. They are as follows:

1. Verno/neverno (true/false) test type - this is a question a correct or incorrect answer is chosen;

2. Oдиноchnyy vybor (selecting one answer) - choosing the desired answer from several options;
3. Mnojestvennyy vybor (selection of several answers);
4. Input stroke (line input) - answer by entering the answer in a line;
5. Sootvetstvie (matching) - an answer that matches the questions with their answers to give
6. Pryadok (order) - give the answer in the required order;
7. Vvod chisla (enter a number) - answer by entering a number corresponding to the answer to the question;
8. Propuski (omitted) - write the omitted words in the right place;
9. Vlojennye otvety (summary answers) – choosing the right answer from the summaries reply via;
10. Bank slov (vocabulary) - find the necessary words from the vocabulary in the correct sequence answer by putting. In this case, it is necessary to add words to the vocabulary.
11. Aktivnaya oblast (active area) - the answer is given by selecting the active area in the picture. In this picture a question in which you need to choose a field is entered.

When creating a test, it is necessary to choose this type of test, ask appropriate questions and enter the answer will be.

In the first step, we select the required type of test from the Dobavit vopros section. For example, verno/neverno type. Then the program window will appear as below

Figure 3. Verno/neverno type

Enter a question in the question box of this window, and according to it, enter two answers in the answer box, choose the correct answer to the question. In the right part of the program window, Image, Sound, Video recording is available with the help of these files by selecting images, formulas, sounds, videos and questions

there is also a possibility to create. In this way, it is possible to create tests by choosing from various test types.

The third step. After the test is created, it needs to be configured. Give an overall score, how many points to assign to each question, the duration of the test, etc. for this again to the Nastroyki department let's enter We can configure our tester by entering the sections on the left side of this window

We can create our created test in four different ways. Web page, iSpring Online, LMS, Word page. After that, we choose the test format HTML, exe, Zip archive, tester name, scope, storage location, file name, and flash drive properties select and press the Publish button.

Conclusion, this test is better than traditional tests there will be no uniformity in the test and students will be given tests in a slightly more interesting way. From him In addition to these interactive tests, it is possible to create tests using pictures, sounds and formulas their presence makes them more interesting and encourages the student to work with great enthusiasm. A test control could be performed using delimited directions from normal tests, e.g For music students, only theoretical questions could be asked and the program has the possibility to create a test with the help of adding sounds, a piece of music creates an opportunity to create questions. Other areas: informatics, mathematics, physics, biology, geography, etc. possibility to create very interesting, interactive tests for there is. In addition, it is possible to conduct the test through computer networks and electronic

The availability of postal services also meets the requirements of today's modern education can answer.

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